

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ANTHROPOCENTRIC PARADIGM IN LINGUISTIC STUDIES

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Abstract: The anthropocentric paradigm, which places humans at the center of linguistic studies, has become a significant approach in contemporary linguistics. This article deduced the development of this paradigm in Uzbek linguistics, examining key research areas such as sociolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, and discourse analysis. By focusing on discourse, semantics, and the study of language as a communicative tool, the article presents a comprehensive view of the role of the human factor in linguistic theory and practice.

Keywords: Anthropocentric paradigm, Uzbek linguistics, sociolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, discourse analysis, psycholinguistics, human-centered approach, language and culture, semantic perception, communication.

Introduction

In today's rapidly developing world, various branches of linguistics, such as linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, ethnolinguistics, neurolinguistics, paralinguistics, and gender linguistics, all center around the human factor as the object of study. The emergence of these fields is closely linked to efforts to study linguistic activity in direct connection with its human subject.

Within the anthropocentric paradigm, humans are placed at the center, and language is seen as a fundamental component that forms the essence of the human being. Since the early years of the 21st century, research in Uzbek linguistics based on the anthropocentric paradigm has begun to emerge. These works are mainly conducted in the fields of sociolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, linguistic pragmatics, and psycholinguistics. Although these studies do not explicitly refer to the anthropocentric paradigm, they are recognized as the first works reflecting the principles of this paradigm.

Research in Sociolinguistics and Psycholinguistics

For example, S.M. Mo'minov's doctoral dissertation on the "Social-linguistic Characteristics of Uzbek Communication Behavior" explores the unique

communication behavior of Uzbeks from a social-linguistic perspective. This research not only highlights the importance of the human factor in linguistic activity but also focuses on studying the linguistic peculiarities of communication processes.

One of the first works in Uzbek linguistics to analyze text from an anthropocentric perspective is I.A. Azimova's dissertation on "The Psycholinguistic Study of the Semantic Perception of Newspaper Texts in Uzbek." The research focuses on identifying linguistic and extralinguistic factors affecting text comprehension through psycholinguistic experiments. This dissertation also analyzes the semantic perception units in a text and their formal-semantic characteristics.

According to I.A. Azimova, words, word forms, phrases, and syntagmas are considered the basic units of semantic perception in texts. Moreover, the dissertation presents an in-depth analysis of the "stimulus linguistic factors in the text" and "the primary processes in text perception."

The Anthropocentric Paradigm and Linguistics

In his article on the study of language through paradigms, the linguist A. Rahimov discusses the anthropocentric paradigm, also known as the communicative or nominative-pragmatic paradigm, in the history of linguistics. According to A. Rahimov, this paradigm views language not as a mere structure but as an open system based on communication and interaction.

A. Rahimov argues that in linguistics, language and various aspects of social life are interconnected, and humans serve as the "golden bridge" between these areas. Therefore, cognitive, sociolinguistic, ethnolinguistic, psycholinguistic, neurolinguistic, pragmatic, and linguoculturological paradigms are seen as sub-paradigms within the broader anthropocentric framework.

In contemporary linguistics, studying language systems from an anthropocentric perspective is primarily found in research on linguistic semantics, cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, pragmatics, and linguoculturology. Renowned Uzbek linguist Prof. N. Mahmudov emphasizes the significance of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics: "According to the objective nature of language, the anthropocentric paradigm places humans at the center, with language being a key element in shaping the human personality."

Anthropocentric Paradigm and Discourse

The essence of the anthropocentric paradigm is explained by the shift from the question "how is language structured?" to "how is language used?" To

understand how language is used, it is necessary to study the speech-cognitive processes of the human being who is its owner. This shift demands a new approach in linguoculturology, particularly in linking language with culture. In anthropocentric linguistics, studying discourse allows for the investigation of human speech from a communicative aspect.

In the 1920s, linguistics began to acknowledge discourse as being related to spoken language, with certain expressions, such as interjections and introductory phrases, marking discourse features. In foreign linguistics, syntactic issues related to discourse were raised by Z. Harris in the 1950s. By the 1970s, discourse and syntax were recognized as separate areas in linguistics.

Discourse and Its Analysis

There are various definitions of discourse. According to J.R. Geary, discourse is the integration of linguistic and extralinguistic factors such as actions, interactions, thinking methods, beliefs, and evaluations necessary for the implementation of specific social roles. V.V. Krasnix views discourse as a linguistic and extralinguistic phenomenon that includes speech activity processes and their outcomes.

Through discourse analysis, the broader linguistic dimensions of speech units, such as sentences, are revealed. The way a person understands and interprets a specific concept within their national-cultural context plays a significant role in the speech process. Pragmatic information and precedent phenomena used in literary texts or communication are always understood by members of a particular society but may be challenging for others outside that cultural context. Sh. Safarov, in his analysis of the nuances of communication processes, acknowledges the existence of a cultural framework specific to each nation. This cultural framework, formed by ethnic-ethical norms, serves as the foundation of communication strategies and tactics. In this regard, the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics is used to study the role of humans in communication and their social, psychological, and cultural aspects. In the 21st century, new approaches to semantics and syntax are emerging in linguistics. Linguists are examining how humans perceive the real world through language and how they convey their thoughts. The questions of how language employs communicative strategies and how it presents specific information to people have become key concerns in linguistic studies.

Conclusion

The anthropocentric paradigm has significantly influenced the development of linguistic studies in Uzbekistan, shaping various fields such as sociolinguistics,

cognitive linguistics, and discourse analysis. This paradigm emphasizes the central role of the human being in language, recognizing the interconnection between linguistic activity, social behavior, cultural norms, and cognitive processes. By focusing on the ways humans understand, interpret, and use language, scholars have been able to develop more nuanced and comprehensive models of communication. As the study of language continues to evolve, the anthropocentric paradigm remains a crucial framework for understanding the complexities of human communication. Its emphasis on the human factor allows for a deeper exploration of language not just as a system of rules, but as a tool for social interaction, cultural expression, and cognitive processing. Therefore, integrating the anthropocentric perspective into contemporary linguistic research promises to yield new discoveries and a more holistic understanding of language as a fundamental aspect of human life. Thus, the anthropocentric paradigm has become one of the key approaches in Uzbek linguistics for studying the relationship between language and the human being. Considering social, psychological, and cognitive factors is crucial for creating new theoretical and practical frameworks in linguistics. The study of language and human interaction, along with the integration of linguistic, cultural, and cognitive contexts, provides a deeper understanding of the role of language in human society.

References:

1. Xudoyberganova D. Lingvokulturologiya terminlarining qisqacha izohli lug'ati. – Toshkent: Turon zamin ziyo, 2015. –5 b.
2. Mo'minov S.M. O'zbek muloqot xulqining ijtimoiy-lisoniy xususiyatlari: Filol. fan. d-ri ... dis. avtoref. – Toshkent: O'zR FA TAI, 2000. – 47 b.
3. Mahmudov N. Tilning mukammal tadqiqi yo'llarini izlab...// O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. –Toshkent, 2012. -№ 5. – 6-7 b.
4. Маслова В. А. Лингвокультурология. Учебное пособие для студентов высших учебных заведений. –М.,2001.– 6 с.
5. Дорофеев Ю. Антропосентризм в лингвистике и предмет когнитивной грамматики. 2008.–60 с.
6. Щерба Л. В. Языковая система и речевая деятельность. – Л.: Наука, 1974. – 428 с; 2-е изд. – М.: УРСС, 2004.
7. Harris Z.S. Analyse du discours // Languages, 1969. – №13. – 8-45 p.
8. Гиндин С.И. Советская лингвистика текста. Некоторые проблемы и результаты (1968-1975) // Известия АН СССР, серия ЛЯ, 1977. – № 4. – 348-361 с.

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9. Колшанский Г.В. Коммуникативная дискретность языка// Лингвистика текста, сб. науч. трудов. Вып. 103. – М: МГПИИЯ, 1976. – 15-22 с.
10. Слюсарев Н.А. Проблемы функционального синтаксиса современного английского языка. – М.: Наука, 1981. – 206 с.
11. Benveniste E. Problèmes de linguistique général. – Paris: Gallimard, 1966. –. 356
12. Safarov Sh. Pragmalingvistika. – Toshkent. 2008. –.267 b.
13. Стародумова Ye. А. Синтаксис современного русского языка. Владивосток, Изд. Дальневосточного университета, 2005 г. 33 с. .
14. Nurmonov A. Tanlangan asarlar. 3-jild, Tilshunoslikning nazariy va amaliy muammolari bo'yicha tanlangan maqolalar. T., 2012 y. – 76 b
15. Gee J. P. An introduction to discourse analysis. Theory and practice. – Routledge, 2005. – 209 p.
16. Красных В. В. Этнопсихоллингвистика и лингвокультурология: Курс лекций. М.: Гнозис, 2002. – 200 с.
17. Карасик В.И. Языковой круг: личность, концепты, дискурс. Волгоград: Перемена, 2002. – 280 с.
18. Kizi, S. B. Y. (2022). Linguo-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette occurring in discourse. Current Research Journal of Philological Sciences, 3(11), 59-63.
19. Bobojonova, S. (2022). Pragmatic interpretation of educational discourse and expression of dialogic discourse in the communication process.
20. Арутюнова Н.Д. Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь. 1990 г. 136-137 с.